

METHODS AND MODELS FOR THE FORMATION AND APPLICATION OF GEOECOLOGICAL MONITORING OF LAND USE BY TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE IN REGIONS

Mamonov K.

*D. Sc. (Econ.), Prof., head of department,
department of land administration and geographic information systems
<http://orcid.org/0000-0002-0797-2609>*

Goi V.

*D. Sc. (Econ.),
department of land administration and geoinformation systems
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1822-4478>*

Nelin Ye.

*postgraduate student,
department of land administration and geoinformation systems
<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-8224-3062>*

Frolov V.

*Cand. Sc. (Tech.), Assist.
department of land administration and geographic information systems
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8045-3963>
O.M. Beketov National University of Urban Economy in Kharkiv, (Ukraine)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17741000>*

Abstract

The relevance of the research topic is determined by the need to introduce and implement geo-ecological monitoring to improve the efficiency of land use for transport infrastructure at the regional level.

The author proposes a definition of geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure in regions as a system consisting of environmental, land, transport infrastructure factors, and technological, spatial, stakeholder structural components aimed at permanent observation and control and the formation of measures to prevent negative phenomena in the land use system using a modern geoinformation system.

The research objective of substantiating methods and models for the formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in regional transport infrastructure has been achieved.

A method has been proposed for assessing the level of development and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in regional transport infrastructure, based on the application of a multi-level system of environmental, land and transport infrastructure indicators, mathematical expert and analytical methods, which made it possible to identify positive forecast trends in the generalising criterion.

A technology has been developed for the formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure at the regional level, which is formed on the basis of information-analytical and spatial support, assessment methods, geoinformation and mathematical tools, the results of modelling forecast changes, which made it possible to develop scenarios for the formation and use of transport infrastructure land, taking into account the ecological state, and to build GIS monitoring maps.

The proposed methods and models of mathematical modelling of formation and application factors provide opportunities to form a quantitative basis for the formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of transport infrastructure land use at the regional level.

Keywords: geoecological monitoring, land use, transport infrastructure, geographic information systems, assessment, geodetic support, methods and models.

Relevance of the research topic. Permanent changes occurring in the field of land relations require a rethinking of approaches to ensuring effective land use through the application of modern tools for making informed decisions. This process is multifaceted and affects the possibilities and directions of the formation and application of geo-ecological monitoring (GM) of land use (LU), in particular in the field of transport infrastructure (TI) functioning in regions. In this context, it is important to develop and implement methods and models for creating a quantitative basis for GM and to apply geoinformation systems to ensure the effectiveness of spatial modelling of TI land use processes at the regional level.

Thus, the research topic is relevant and timely for the development of modern geo-ecological monitoring

systems for the use of land for regional transport infrastructure.

Statement of the problem. Existing scientific studies lack a unified approach to defining geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure in regions. Problematic aspects of land monitoring, taking into account the specifics of its use, are highlighted in works [1, 2].

Information support for land monitoring has been developed, as discussed in [3, 4].

The functional aspects of land monitoring have been identified, which are aimed at continuous surveying of the state and land use, identification of negative processes for the development of measures and counteraction to deformation processes [5]. As a system for ensuring control functions, their

implementation is determined by land monitoring in the work [6].

A systematic approach to defining land monitoring is implemented in [7]. Developing a systematic approach, it is worth noting the definition, where land monitoring is characterised as a complex, constantly transforming category that includes a set of interrelated actions aimed at ensuring control over the state and use of land resources, the elimination of negative phenomena and their prevention at various territorial levels, which are implemented on the basis of information and analytical and regulatory and legal support, including qualitative, functional, socio-economic, natural, infrastructural, and urban planning characteristics [8].

Thus, the author proposes a definition of geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure in regions as a system consisting of environmental, land, transport infrastructure factors, and technological, spatial, stakeholder structural components aimed at permanent observation and control and the formation of measures to prevent negative phenomena in the land use system using a modern geoinformation system.

The international experience in the formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in regional transport infrastructure has been summarised. Its implementation has been found to be unsystematic, focusing only on individual elements: environmental, spatial, and transport, taking into account the peculiarities of the distribution and use of land resources.

It has been established that in order to ensure geo-ecological monitoring in international practices, regulatory and legal support, instrumental and functional directions are justified, a licensing system is characterised, and a strategy of environmentally oriented management and environmental entrepreneurship is applied. The following elements of monitoring procedures in the context of environmental policy development and implementation have been identified: LIFE, environmental protection agreements, environmental duties and taxes, a programme to support NGOs active in the field of environmental protection, integrated product policy (Integrated Product Policy), the functioning of the European Environment Agency, eco-labelling of products, the development of the Community's environmental management and audit system (EMAS), environmental impact assessment (EIA), assessment of the environmental consequences of the implementation of plans and programmes, environmental audits – minimum criteria, European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (PRTR).

Proposed technologies for the development and implementation of environmental monitoring: Smart application tools; GIS analysis and modelling; digitisation of the environment; formation of a digital reality of the environment; innovative tools for digital reality technologies. In addition, the directions and features of waste management are characterised.

Monitoring of transport systems, taking into account international experience, is carried out through

the prism of the directions and features of institutional policy implementation, transport infrastructure development planning, taxation, pricing, and cost reimbursement.

Modern technologies are proposed to ensure the monitoring of transport infrastructure, in particular, the use of UAVs: inspection and calibration of precision approach path indicators (PAPI); airfield lighting systems (ALS); instrument landing systems (ILS); ultra-shortwave radio equipment (VOR) systems for collecting electronic data on terrain and obstacles (electronic terrain and obstacle data (eTOD)).

Purpose and objectives of the study. The purpose of the study is to substantiate methods and models for the formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in regional transport infrastructure. The following tasks were solved in the study:

- to propose a multi-level system of indicators for the formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in regional transport infrastructure;
- to develop a method for assessing the level of formation and implementation of GM LU TI;
- to propose a method and models for the integrated assessment of the level of formation and application of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in transport infrastructure by region;
- to determine the stages of mathematical modelling of the factors of formation and implementation of GM LU TI of regions;
- to propose a technology for the formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in the transport infrastructure of regions;
- to determine the directions and features of the application of geographic information systems in GM.

Main part. A multi-level system of indicators for the formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in regional transport infrastructure has been developed, which is determined by environmental, land and transport infrastructure use factors and is characterised by local, consolidated and integrated levels. The developed multi-level system of indicators allows to form the basis for assessing the level of formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in the transport infrastructure of regions.

The proposed stages of development and implementation of the method for assessing the level of formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in the transport infrastructure of regions. As a result of assessing the integral indicator of the level of formation and application of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in the transport infrastructure of regions, an increase in crisis phenomena has been established, which manifests itself in frontline regions, areas where hostilities are taking place, or in occupied territories. In most regions, the level of formation and application of geo-ecological monitoring is insignificant.

A method and models for the integrated assessment of the level of formation and application of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in transport

infrastructure by region have been developed and applied. This has made it possible to form a quantitative basis for modelling and forecasting changes in factors and developing measures to improve the efficiency of land use in transport infrastructure using geo-ecological monitoring tools.

The proposed stages of mathematical modelling of the factors of formation and application of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in transport infrastructure in regions. The application of mathematical modelling tools made it possible to form a quantitative basis for the development of measures to improve the effectiveness of the formation and application of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in transport infrastructure at the regional level.

As a result of the study, quantitative parameters for increasing the level of formation and application of geo-ecological monitoring to improve the efficiency of land use for transport infrastructure at the regional level have been determined.

A technology has been proposed for the development and implementation of GM LU for the transport infrastructure of regions, which is formed on the basis of analytical and spatial information, creating information, analytical and spatial support for geo-ecological monitoring. An important element of the technology is the application of a method for assessing the level of formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure.

Proposed scenarios for the formation and use of transport infrastructure land, taking into account the environmental situation, according to established regional clusters: negative: cluster 2 (Dnipropetrovsk, Sumy, Zaporizhzhia, Mykolaiv, Kharkiv regions); cluster 5 (Kherson, Luhansk, Donetsk); stagnant: cluster 1 (Vinnytsia, Lviv, Volyn, Zhytomyr, Ivano-Frankivsk, Khmelnytskyi); cluster 3 (Kyiv, Ternopil, Rivne, Chernihiv); cluster 4 (Kirovohrad, Odesa, Poltava, Zakarpattia, Cherkasy, Chernivtsi). The absence of regions that correspond to the development scenario has been identified. In this context, measures have been proposed to improve the effectiveness of the formation and implementation of scientifically based measures for the application of GM LU transport infrastructure at the regional level.

The stages of development of geoinformation monitoring maps of transport infrastructure land use, taking into account the environmental situation, have been identified: application of a quantitative basis for the development of GM LU transport infrastructure at the regional level; determination of software for the development of GIS monitoring maps using the Q GIS software complex; development of attribute information determined by the factors of formation and application of geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure at the regional level; formation of GIS monitoring map layers; presentation of geoinformation monitoring maps of land use for transport infrastructure, taking into account the ecological situation.

As a result of the study, GIS monitoring maps of factors of geo-ecological monitoring of land use by

transport infrastructure at the regional level were constructed, the application of which made it possible to track the directions and processes of changes in the environment, the implementation of environmental processes and the functioning of transport infrastructure. The possibilities for the implementation and application of geoinformation systems to ensure the monitoring of the environmental state of transport infrastructure have been identified. The developed GIS monitoring maps ensure an increase in the efficiency of the construction and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure at the regional level.

Regions classified by security level: none (Luhansk, Donetsk); low (Zaporizhzhia, Kherson, Sumy, Kharkiv); insignificant (Mykolaiv, Odesa, Dnipropetrovsk); minor (Chernihiv, Kyiv); low-medium (Zhytomyr, Poltava); medium (Kirovohrad, Cherkasy, Vinnytsia, Volyn, Rivne, Lviv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Ternopil, Khmelnytskyi); high-medium (Zakarpattia, Chernivtsi). GIS monitoring maps of the security level of regions were created, which made it possible to propose the location of transport logistics centres in the Zakarpattia and Chernivtsi regions. In addition, given the technical security capabilities, there are opportunities to relocate or place transport logistics centres, taking into account environmental parameters, in the Kirovohrad, Cherkasy, Vinnytsia, Volyn, Rivne, Lviv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Ternopil and Khmelnytskyi regions.

Conclusions. Thus, the categorical apparatus for determining the geo-ecological monitoring of land use in the transport infrastructure of regions has been improved, based on the results of systematising theoretical and methodological approaches, the application of geoinformation and mathematical tools, taking into account the influence of environmental, land and transport infrastructure factors, which made it possible to form a scientific basis for the development and implementation of GM technology to increase the efficiency of TI land use.

A typological structure of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in transport infrastructure in regions has been developed, which is determined by environmental, land and transport infrastructure factors, allowing the formation of a quantitative basis for assessing the level of GM application.

A method has been proposed for assessing the level of development and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use in the transport infrastructure of regions, based on the application of a multi-level system of environmental, land and transport infrastructure indicators, mathematical expert and analytical methods, which made it possible to identify positive forecast trends in the generalised criterion of GM LU TI.

A technology has been developed for the formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure at the regional level, which is based on information and analytical and spatial support, assessment methods, geoinformation and mathematical tools, the results of modelling forecast changes, which made it possible to

develop scenarios for the formation and implementation of TI, taking into account the ecological state, and to build GIS monitoring maps.

The proposed methods and models of mathematical modelling of the factors of formation and application provide opportunities to form a quantitative basis for the formation and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of land use by transport infrastructure at the regional level.

References:

1. Overkovska T. (2015) Monitoring of Ukrainian lands: legal aspects. *Legal Gazette. Air and Space Law.* 1, 125–128. http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Npnau_2015_1_25.
2. Granovskaya L., Vashchenko Yu. (2014) Water management and land reclamation complex as a complex ecological and economic system: theoretical aspect. *Irrigated agriculture* 61, 143–146. http://izpr.ks.ua/archive/2014/61/61_2014.pdf
3. Novakovska I., Bulgakov V., Ivanov S., Dukulis I. (2018) Formation of sustainable land-use systems in erosion dangerous landscapes. *17 International Scientific Conference «Engineering for rural development».* Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies Faculty of Engineering, 378 – 386. <https://doi.org/10.22616/ERDev2018.17N486>
4. Martin A., Kubakh S. (2018) Land management and land valuation in Ukraine: systematic deregulation is needed. *Land Management Bulletin.* 10, 24–29.
5. Gorbatyuk V., Klymenko K. (2007) Organisational and technological features of land monitoring at the regional level. *Geodesy, cartography and aerial photography.* 69, 150–156. <http://ena.lp.edu.ua:8080/bitstream/ntb/1459/1/23.pdf>
6. Pakhomov V. (2018) Land monitoring as an important tool for improving the control and supervision system in Ukraine. *Legal horizons.* 12(25), 16–21. <http://www.doi.org/10.21272/legalhorizons.2018.i12.p16>
7. Romanko R., Petrakovska O. (2013) Methods and models for monitoring lands affected by exogenous geological processes. *Science and Education a New Dimension: Natural and Technical Sciences,* 15, 134–137. https://seanewdim.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/seanewdim_nat_ma_tech_i2_issue_15_2013.pdf
8. Mamonov K. (2016) Definition of land monitoring in the land management system in Ukraine. *Highways and Road Construction.* 97, 55–62. http://publications.ntu.edu.ua/avtodorogi_i_stroitelstvo/97/055-062.pdf